

DELIVERABLE

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Report about working holographic sorter configuration

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0.2	7/3/2018	V. Grillo	CNR	Programming fan out sorter
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0.4	5/4/2018	A. Tavabi	FZJ	Information about experiments
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is 1) to demonstrate the design study and 2) the realization of an OAM sorter through SiN based electron holograms.

The long term objectives are to 1) use the holographic configuration as a starting point for the electrostatic one, and 2) to have viable alternative for experiments on dichroism in case of delay in the realization of the e.m. version of the sorter. In this context, by using innovative design, we tried to implement a fan-out version of the sorter with potentially more OAM resolution that could be beneficial in dichroism experiments.

This deliverable complies with the Q-SORT description of work outlined in *Work Package 2: “Design and implementation of prototype holographic and electromagnetic sorter”* and in particular *Task 2.2 “Fabrication and testing of standard holographic OAM sorting configuration”*.

It is intended to directly benefit the work of the following related tasks:

- *Task 2.5 [Testing and implementation of the new phase elements in a TEM]. Potentially it can be used in contingency case for*
- *WP4 entirely [Early validation and key application of the sorter in material Science]*
- *Task 5.3 [Experimental application of the Sorter to the protein orientation problem]*

The current document comprises 5 main Chapters, an Executive Summary and the Conclusions.

The first chapter introduces the OAM sorter with its potential problems while in the second chapter we describe the model and the simulation aiming to estimate the optimal sorter parameters.

The third chapter describes the implementation of the standard OAM sorter within the microscope in a working configuration, i.e. allowing the sample to be placed in its conventional position.

The fourth chapter describes the implementation of a new version of the Sorter called fan-out, potentially allowing for a better OAM resolution.

In fifth and last chapter we report on a performance test of the OAM sorter by using standard and programmable vortex structures.

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is based on two main results: the previous results on the sorter in a different optical configuration [1] and the calculation of the electro-optical configuration within the microscope [2].

In a previous paper, [1] we realized the sorter configuration using holograms located in the sample and selected area position. The Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) was operated in the “low mag” electro-optical lens configuration, namely with objective lens switched off.

This demonstration, however, is not very useful for the purposes of the project since we would like to use the sample position for the sample to be analyzed.

In order to preserve the functionality of the microscope, the first sorting hologram must be placed in the objective focal plane while the second may remain in the in the SAD aperture plane.

The previous results show that there is a limited set of sorter parameters that can be reached by nanofabrication and therefore we need to realize the largest effective focal as possible.

Thanks to the XL lens, and in some cases by turning off the aberration corrector, we can realize a focal of the order of 1m.

2. HOLOGRAM MODELS AND SIMULATION

In addition to the standard model of sorter we also studied the possibility of an improved version. In fact, the resolution of a standard OAM-Sorter is quite poor: two beams with $L=1$ and $L=0$ produce two partially overlapped peaks with a cross talk of 20 -30%.

In the electrostatic version of the sorter the background due to the interaction of the electron beam with the silicon nitride support is absent, then the signal in the sorter 1 and sorter 2 planes will certainly be more clean than in the holographic one, so it would seem to be useless to create the holographic sorter if this is not better than the electrostatic version.

However, holograms allow for a larger flexibility in the design of the phase so that we can try to improve them by designing a more sophisticated sorter.

In optics, the ideal solution for an improved OAM sorter comes from the papers of the Boyd's group [3] where four holograms are used to produce 9 equal copies of the sorted beam in order to produce more OAM resolved results. Because the beam copies are tiled with respect to the original one this configuration takes the name of fan-out.

In electron microscopy, due to a combination of dimensional and magnetic lens flexibility constraint, it is complicated to introduce four holograms along the electron path, but fortunately following recent results reported in optics [4], we can compactify the transformation using only 2 holograms.

Mathematically the phase profiles of the standard OAM sorters are written as

$$\varphi_1 = \left(2\pi \frac{a}{\lambda f} \left[y \operatorname{atan} \left(\frac{y}{x} \right) - x \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{b} \right) + x \right] \right)$$

$$\varphi_2 = \left(2\pi \frac{ab}{\lambda f} \exp \left(-\frac{u}{a} \right) \cos \left(\frac{v}{a} \right) \right)$$

The first phase element performs the conformal mapping from Cartesian coordinates (x,y) to log-polar (u,v) coordinates defined as:

$$u = -\frac{a}{2\pi} \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{b} \right), \text{ and } v = \frac{a}{2\pi} \operatorname{arctan}(x, y)$$

where λ is the wavelength of the incoming beam and f is the focal length of the Fourier transforming lens inserted between the two phase elements, a is the length of the transformed beam, b translates the transformed image in the u direction and can be chosen independently of a . The required phase correction is performed by the second phase element.

We can adopt, for example, a sinusoidal hologram and write

$$S_1 = \sin \left(2\pi \frac{a}{\lambda f} \left[y \operatorname{atan} \left(\frac{y}{x} \right) - x \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{b} \right) + x \right] \right)$$

$$S_2 = \sin \left(2\pi \frac{ab}{\lambda f} \exp \left(-\frac{u}{a} \right) \cos \left(\frac{v}{a} \right) + cx \right)$$

Fig 1 a,b Calculated shape of the OAM sorter 1 and sorter 2 .

For practical reasons we adopt the dimensionless parameter

$$a' = 2\pi \frac{a}{\lambda f} R$$

and we fix both the radius, R , of the hologram (i.e. the maximum value of x and y) and the focal f to a value of $7 \mu\text{m}$ and about 1m , respectively. A series of fabrication tests shows that, due to limitations in the number of pixel addressable with the Focused Ion Beam used to mill the holograms, we can typically produce hologram only if $a > 1$.

In the fan-out version of the sorter, following [4], the first element can be produced using a phase-only blazed hologram

$$S_1 = \text{mod} \left(2\pi \frac{a}{\lambda f} \left[y \text{atan} \left(\frac{y}{x} \right) - x \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2}}{b} \right) + x \right], 2\pi \right) + F \sin(kx + p)$$

and the second sorter then is

$$S_2 = \sin \left(2\pi \frac{ab}{\lambda f} \exp \left(-\frac{u}{a} \right) \cos \left(\frac{v}{a} \right) + cx + \phi(u) \right)$$

Where

$$\phi(u) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } |u| < \frac{a}{4\pi} \\ \frac{\pi}{2} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

While a and b are the same as in the standard sorter, the first hologram of the sorter in the fan-out version has two extra parameters, F and p . The term $F \sin(kx + p)$ gives rise to different diffraction orders n with amplitude given by the Bessel function of the first kind $J_n(F)$. For a correct working of the fan-out the 2 first orders and the order zero must have similar intensity. For $F=1.4$ the second order is still quite small namely 15% of the 0th and 1st order.

Fig 2. Plot of the Bessel function of the first kind. The J_n Bessel function describes the amplitude of the n -th diffraction order of a sinusoidal phase grating as a function of the phase scaling of the grating.

Fig 3 Procedure to obtain the fan-out version of the first sorter hologram. The normal sorter is multiplied by a sinusoidal grating.

3. SIMPLE SORTER

Fig. 4 a,b show the sorter holograms as seen by the electron microscope when mounted directly in the column.

The first hologram (Fig.4a) is imaged slightly out of focus. In this case the relevant calculation parameters are $a' = 5$ and $b = 10 \mu m$.

The use of the sinusoidal holograms produces a diffraction pattern with similar intensity for both the +1 and -1 diffraction orders that are visible in fig. 5 as two parallel straight lines.

When the second hologram of the sorter is superimposed to the diffraction pattern of the first sorter hologram only the 1st and 0th order of its diffraction are visible (see fig 5b) since the -1st is practically absorbed by the unprocessed part of the silicon nitride substrate Fig. 6 shows the spectrum of the OAM on the right as a peak (it is just the OAM analysis of the plane wave). The big central disk is a shadow image of the beam itself while the faint spot on the left is the -1st order diffraction of the second hologram.

In order to optimize the alignment between the diffraction pattern of the first hologram of the sorter and the second hologram we fabricate six copies of the second one rotated of 20 degrees with respect to each other.

Fig 4. TEM image of the first (a) and second (b) hologram of the sorter

Fig. 5 a) Diffraction from the first hologram of the sorter: the two very bright straight lines are the two first order diffracted beam showing the log-polar transformed beam. b) Superposition of the diffraction of the first hologram with the second hologram.

Fig 6 Diffraction pattern observed after the second hologram of the sorter consisting of the shadow image of the first hologram (center) and the OAM spectrum (right encircled).

4. FAN-OUT SORTER

The fan-out sorter is again comprised of two elements, but the second hologram is more elongated than the standard version in order to accommodate the three copies of the beam diffracted by the first hologram.

The TEM image of the first hologram of the fan-out sorter hologram is shown in Fig 7a. A detail of the central part of the sorter is shown in fig 7b. Here the sinusoidal carrier wave, made by vertical lines, is clearly visible.

Fig 7 Example of fan-out sorter hologram S1(a,b) and S2 (c). The image b is a detail of the central part of S1

Fig 8 Diffraction pattern of the first hologram of the fan-out sorter. The upper line is the first order of diffraction and is made of three distinct segments. These are the three copies of the log-polar transformed beam. Ideally they should have the same intensity. This condition is only approximately realized. The 0th and -1st order appear also in three copies. The -1st order is also quite faint as an effect of the blazed grating profile. The efficiency of the 1st order is about 60% of the overall intensity.

Fig. 7c shows the TEM image of the second hologram of the fan-out sorter. The hologram is characterized by three regions separated by a discontinuity on the hologram lines. These three regions will be aligned with the corresponding three copies of the beam of the transformed beam produced by the first hologram of the fan-out sorter. The diffraction pattern of the first hologram is indeed visible in Fig 8. Since in this case the hologram is characterized by a blazed shape of the groove, the upper orders are more intense than the lower ones. Since the hologram has been calculated as a perfectly blazed hologram with discontinuity of exactly 2π we have optimized the milling depth in order to have as much as possible of the intensity concentrated on the 1st order. If this optimization is performed the intensity of the three beams results also quite similar as strongly requested by the sorter design.

The OAM spectrum is then visible in Fig 9 as the dot on the right. The 0th order is just a shadow image of the beam. In this case the beam is a vortex beam generated by an electrostatic vortex generator EVG [5] whose main metallic arm is visible as a black rectangular shadow.

Fig 9 Diffraction after the S2 hologram consisting of the shadow image of S1 hologram (center) and the OAM spectrum (right).

5. TESTING

Thanks to the use of the use of the EVG we can test the sorter using different vortexes with a minimal change of the configuration. In this way we were able to produce the graph below

Fig. 10 OAM Spectrum for different vortexes produced by the EVG. The main peaks separation is compatible with normal OAM sorter (i.e. no fan- out) but a further broadening is visible below the main peak.

In the figure, the peaks correspond to different values of the OAM. While the peaks are well separated, the tails are largely overlapped. This is indeed one of the early OAM sorter fan-out where the thickness was still not perfectly optimized.

It is possible also to appreciate that the peaks tend to decrease in intensity when getting far from the peak for $L=0$. This is indeed an effect of the limited precision of the sorter hologram S2 that is not able to transfer very high frequencies.

Fig. 11 Comparison between the central peak of the OAM spectrum in figure 10 (blue line) and expected peak shape obtained by simulating the standard sorter and the fan-out configuration (black and red line respectively).

It turns out that the central peak performs better than a normal sorter but worse than an ideal fan-out.

However the tails are by far too large. The possible reason could be:

1. Alignment (1° - 2° off and/or 5% dimension mismatch are sufficient to produce the large tails)
2. Aberrations (the images in log-polar coordinates shows some deformation not expected in simulation)
3. Spurious tilt could also affect the overall result and are difficult to control
4. Imperfections in the holograms can be also to blame for non-perfect functioning

We think that, in order to rule out most of the instrumental effects, it will be necessary to compare it with the electrostatic version of the OAM sorter.

The separation for this early scheme is still quite low. This means that there is space for further improvement of the sorter.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable we have shown that both the standard and fan-out versions of the OAM sorter can be demonstrated and work in TEM standard conditions, namely with the sample between the microscope polar expansions. Consequently the two holograms S1 and S2 are in the objective and SAD aperture positions, exactly as it will be for the electro-magnetic implementation and as calculated with the ray tracing in deliverable D2.1.

The use of many holographic elements with different orientations, turned out to be the best approach to face the problem of the precise orientation of the two phase elements.

The use of the fan-out version is the best approach to obtain a potentially cross talk free control of the OAM of the final state.

At the moment the resolution seems to be still not so impressive with a partial superposition of the tails of vortexes with different OAM. This is most probably because of the imperfections in the calibration of the phase elements but the further development of the manufacture of the hologram should allow for an OAM measurement potentially better than the case of E.m. sorter and represent a realistic alternative in some cases.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Grillo et al., Nature Communications **8**, 15536 (2017)
- [2] QSORT Deliverable D2.1
- [3] M. Mirhosseini et al. Nature Communications **4**, 2781 (2013)
- [4] G. Ruffato et al. Sci Rep. **8**,10248 (2018) |
- [5] G. Pozzi *et al.* Ultramic. 181, 191 (2017)

ANNEX 1: REFEREE

Daan Stellinga (UG)

I like the general idea of combining the established technologies of a two-element OAM sorter and silicon nitride phase masks; and the development of specific versions of these phase masks that are compatible with current TEM systems, especially in a way that leaves a sample position available in order to actually make use of the sorting seems like a very worthwhile direction to push this research in. The results presented here look like a very good first push in the direction of making these systems viable, with significant progress towards a sorter with very little to no cross talk. Unfortunately, the current presentation of the excellent progress in this direction slightly obfuscates the actual achievements.

Below I've made a list of some more specific minor changes to the presentation that I would suggest to increase the appeal of the report. Most of these changes highlight statements that I believe could use a few extra sentences to clarify for someone less familiar with the work.

We thank the referee for the comments. The answers are reported in Italic below

Introduction

- 1) I would suggest including an actual reference to the "previous paper" mentioned here. More generally, references seem to be missing from the report?

Following the referee's suggestion we added references through the paper where needed.

Hologram models and simulation

- 1) Why would the electrostatic version be more "clean"? What does "clean" actually mean in this context? And if this is obvious, then what aspect do you think the holographic version could improve on? Spending an extra sentence or two to properly explain such statements would make them far more convincing to me.

"With " clean" we mean that in the case of em sorter the OAM spectrum will not be affected by the background generated by electron-matter scattering. A sentence has been inserted into the text.

- 2) I believe the first "fan-out" sorter paper used four phase elements with 9 copies of the original beam? (Bob Boyd's group, Optics Express, 2012, <https://www.osapublishing.org/oe/abstract.cfm?uri=oe-20-22-24444>). I could be wrong though.

We have inserted the Nat. Comm. paper by Boyd group (the last paper on the subject) in the reference list.

- 3) "In electron microscopy it is complicated to introduce 3 holograms but fortunately we can compactify the transformation using only 2 holograms." As with comment 1, statements like these are more convincing if a reason is given for the problems mentioned. I.e. why is complicated to introduce 3 holograms but not 2?

A sentence has been inserted to clarify this point: "In electron microscopy, due to a combination of TEM structure constraint and magnetic lens flexibility, it is complicated to introduce four holograms along the electron path, but fortunately following recent results reported in optics [4], we can compactify the transformation using only two holograms.

- 4) The first ph1 here has a random multiplication by "1"?

The "1" has been removed.

- 5) Again a more general comment: it would be useful if you could define the variables used in equations when they're first introduced.

We inserted the missing definitions.

- 6) What are the limitations you run into with the fabrication? Is this due to a resolution limit of the fabrication method, or a structural limitation of the silicon nitride membranes, or something else? It would also be informative to give a little bit of information about what fabrication method is actually being used, and if this is the best technique for the task.

A sentence has been inserted: A series of fabrication tests shows that, due to limitations in the number of pixel addressable with the Focused Ion Beam used to mill the holograms, we can typical produce hologram only if $a' > 1$.

- 7) It seems unnecessary to me to mention an alternative method of creating the fan-out element, but if you do include it I'd suggest explaining why the chosen method is more practical a little bit more extensively.

We agree with the referee. The alternative method has been removed.

Simple sorter

- 1) I believe "b" needs units of length here (um?) ?

The referee is correct. We specified the correct unit.

- 2) Why is the -1st order not visible in figure 5b? Is that expected or does it imply a problem?

The -1st is not visible since it is superimposed to the thick part of the hologram. A sentence has been added.

- 3) Figure 6 doesn't really seem to add much in it's current form, as the image shows no indication of whether the simple sorter does what it's supposed to do, or how well it does it. Adding a

comparison picture with an OAM beam would make this more useful, but on its own I'm not sure I would include it in the report.

The aim of this part of the deliverable was to demonstrate the realization of the experiment with two phase element inserted in the objective focal plane and in the selected area aperture of the microscope, without any sample. Figure 6 was intended to show the most important images of the experiment i.e. diffraction of Sorter 1, alignment of this image with Sorter 2 and the diffraction pattern with Sorted 1 and sorter 2 inserted into the electron optical column.

Fan-out sorter

- 1) Figure 8's caption mentions the phrase "log-polar transformed beam" for the first and only time in the report, without explanation. I would suggest either introducing that phrase in the initial discussion of the sorter designs, or leaving it out of the report altogether.

We have added the definition of log-polar transformed beam in the presentation of the simple sorter.

Testing

- 1) Figure 10 would be far more informative if it was shown alongside a similar plot for the "normal" OAM sorter. It could also use a legend/labels for the different curves. As it stands the caption claims that these results are an improvement over the simple sorter, but there is no way for the reader to verify that for themselves.
- 2) As the goal is to show that the fan-out version is an improvement over the simple version, it seems useful to give some qualitative number of what has actually been achieved? In theory I believe an ideal 3-arm fan-out sorter should have peaks that are 1/3 of the width of a simple-sorter, and the cross-talk therefore should be close to 0% (or at least significantly below the 20-30% of a standard OAM sorter). Obviously from figure 10 this wasn't quite achieved, but if there are numbers along these lines that quantify the improvement achieved that would help.

These points have been raised by the second referee too. We add comments in the text. Please see the answer to the second referee.

- 3) I don't understand figure 11 or how it ties into the rest of the report to be honest.

Fig. 11 has been removed.

Conclusions

"The use of many holographic elements with different orientation turned out to be the best approach to solve the problem of the precise orientation of the two phase elements."
I don't think this was mentioned anywhere before the conclusions?

We add a sentence in the part dedicated to the simple sorter. The same procedure has been used in the fan-out configuration: "In order to optimize the alignment between the diffraction pattern of the first hologram of the sorter and the second hologram we fabricate six copies of the second one rotated of 20 degrees with respect to each other."

Ebrahim Karimi (EAB)

- 1) The deliverable describes the creation of the phase elements and their alignment inside an electron microscopy column for the production of the electron OAM sorter.
- 2) The results are very important in the project and I'd like to compare them to the light optics counterpart.
- 3) The main question is indeed why the resolution is still not ideal even when using a fan out version.
- 4) Can you compare this with simulations? why the tail are still so large ?

Answer

We thank the referee for the comments.

We indeed compared the results of the most recent fan-out OAM sorter with simulation. The comparison is shown in the figure below

It turns out that the central peak performs better than a normal sorter but worse than an ideal fan-out.

However the tail are by far too large. The possible reason could be

1. Alignment (1° - 2° off and/or 5% dimension mismatch are sufficient to produce the large tails)
2. Aberrations (the images in log-polar coordinates shows some deformation not expected in simulation)
3. Spurious tilt could also affect the overall result and are difficult to control
4. Imperfections in the holograms can be also to blame for non-perfect functioning

We think that in order to rule out most of the instrumental effect it will be necessary to compare with the electrostatic OAM sorter.

ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Multi Modal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL